

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable D2.4

Linkage and feature extraction from gut-brain, intermediate evaluation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the intermediate outcomes of Deliverable 2.4 in Work Package 2, which aims to characterise and predict gut–brain linkage in large, deeply phenotyped cohorts. Building on earlier multimodal integration (Deliverable 2.3), we optimized the analysis pipeline by applying Supervised Linked Independent Component Analysis (SuperBigFLICA) to integrate resting-state fMRI networks, gut microbiota relative abundance, and, importantly, tune into behavioural and physiological indices from the Healthy Brain Study (HBS). This approach allows the identification of latent multivariate components that jointly capture microbiome composition, brain-network connectivity, and individual differences in stress-, affect-, and metabolism-related traits.

In order to appropriately handle with the richness of the data and to detect reliable, meaningful physiological patterns, we first explored the model space for models that are physiologically meaningful and robust. Using 4,270 supervised multimodal models and extensive filtering based on reconstruction accuracy, modality mixture, stability, and predictive performance, we identified robust model clusters. Subsequent UMAP-based clustering revealed representative centroid models that were examined in detail. One model (Model 3280), which is representative of a cluster of stable and physiologically plausible models, contained a key latent component (Component 93) that combined strong contributions from gut microbial taxa with connectivity patterns in limbic and default mode networks—regions central to reward valuation and affect regulation. This component was also strongly associated with BMI, anxiety sensitivity, and life event impact.

Critically, Component 93 significantly predicted valuation and choice of unhealthy foods in an independent behavioural task, demonstrating that multimodal gut–brain phenotypes can most likely meaningfully explain variation in eating behaviour; a phenotype on which the model was not trained. These findings validate the feasibility of supervised multimodal integration and identify promising biological targets for follow-up analyses. Ongoing work will evaluate the robustness of the discovered components, apply them to clinical MindSet data, and extend analyses to metabolic markers and future hypotheses-driven studies on stress, diet, and hedonic eating.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Original version
ASI	Anxiety Sensitivity Index
BMI	Body Mass Index
CLR	Centered Log-Ratio (transformation)
DMN	Default Mode Network
ECN	Executive Control Network
FAT	Food Auction Task
fMRI	Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
HBS	Healthy Brain Study
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
IDP	Imaging-Derived Phenotype
LN	Limbic Network
LICA	Linked Independent Component Analysis
nIDP	Non-Imaging-Derived Phenotype
RSN	Resting-State Network
SECPT	Socially Evaluated Cold Pressor Task
SN	Saliency Network
SuperBigFLICA	Supervised Linked Independent Component Analysis
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
WP	Work Package

1 Project outline

Within the HEREDITARY project, we aim to extend earlier work on gut-brain linkage to a larger sample, broadening it to the analysis of brain structure and function in relation to gut microbiota relative abundance and diversity measures together with metabolic parameters. For this we will analyze Healthy Brain Study (HBS; Healthy Brain Study Consortium et al., 2022) and Mindset data (van Oort et al., 2020). HBS is a cohort of 900 deeply phenotyped, healthy individuals in their thirties measured 3 times throughout one year. Mindset is a dataset of >200 psychiatric in-patients with behavioral, clinical, imaging and feces sampling (see D2.20, Boleij et al., (2025), for details on the datasets).

We will integrate the gut microbiota parameters with resting state networks using Linked Independent Component Analyses (LICA). In a first step, once the microbiome data is analyzed and validated, we aimed to characterize gut-brain linkage via LICA with integration of the rich behavior, clinical and physiological data of the HBS cohort. This has been completed in D2.3, see Kohn et al. (2024). In a further step, for D2.4 we have optimized the data integration by supervised learning to increase the predictive value of behavioural and clinical phenotypes. In later stages, we aim to apply and test other multimodal machine learning algorithms aimed at establishing robustness of modality integration across methods, and also to explore utility in the context of federated learning.

1.1 Intermediate analyses

Building on the initial multimodal integration performed in D2.3, the current intermediate analyses expand the data integration framework by incorporating supervised multimodal learning to optimize gut-brain linkage detection. Specifically, we applied Supervised Linked Independent Component Analysis (SuperBigFLICA; Gong et al., 2023) to jointly decompose resting-state fMRI connectivity patterns and gut microbiota relative abundance while guiding the decomposition using behavioural, psychological and physiological phenotypes from the HBS cohort.

For these intermediate analyses, we used the full set of Imaging-Derived Phenotypes (IDPs) derived from four large-scale brain networks—the Salience Network (SN), Default Mode Network (DMN), Executive Control Network (ECN), and Limbic Network (LN)—extracted through Instantaneous Connectivity Parcellation (van Oort et al., 2018) and group ICA procedures (Groves et al., 2011; Kohn et al., 2021). Gut microbiota composition (16S rRNA sequencing, V3–V4) was processed using centered log-ratio transformations and bacterial taxa at genus level present in at least 30% of the samples were retained (N=64 genera). In the framework of the SuperBigFLICA, the gut microbiota is entered among the IDPs, although it is strictly speaking not imaging derived.

Supervision of the FLICA decomposition was provided by 12 non-imaging phenotypes (nIDPs), including anxiety, perceived stress, life event impact, BMI, kilocaloric intake, blood pressure, and cognitive control scores (HBS consortium paper, 2020). The nIDPs represent behavioural and physiological variables that the SuperBigFLICA is tuned to predict. Stress-reactivity measures from the socially evaluated cold pressor task (SECPT; Schwabe et al., 2008) were excluded based on failed manipulation checks. These manipulation checks indicated that the stress induction procedure in the HBS did not lead to a homogenous effect and inclusion of this measure would likely increase noise.

A large-scale hyperparameter grid was evaluated (4,270 models), varying latent dimensionality, regularization parameters, sparsity constraints and learning rates. To reduce and explain the dimensionality of the models, as well as isolate models that were stable, interpretable, and physiologically meaningful, we applied model filtering to this model space.

We filtered the models based on several criteria. For physiological plausibility, we chose to look at how well the models reconstructed the original input data of brain and gut. For this, the SuperBigFlica provides a measure of error of reconstruction and an error in the sparsity of the reconstruction. For the reliability, we filtered models by their correlation between test and training data. Since we are interested in gut-brain linkage, only models with non-arbitrary linkage (proportion of brain or gut > .1) were chosen. These variables were the criteria for selecting certain models. Next to these variables, we also show technical aspects such as learning rate and model size (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Models before and after filtering.

The figure shows the selected models with a least 15% of mixture between brain and gut-related information (in green). A) the total correlation of the nIDPs obtained from the test dataset and the error of the reconstruction of the IDPs (first lambda); b) error of the reconstruction of the nIDPs (third lambda); c) the error from the sparsity of the IDPs (second lambda); d) the error of the sparsity of the nIDPs (fourth lambda); e) the learning rate; f) the number of latent component used. The models in gray were not selected because high error and/or poor number of components with mixture found.

Subsequently, to further examine this model space and identify representative exemplars, we used Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) on the surviving model configurations, configurations to cluster and project model 11 parameters (number of latent components, learning rates, the four lambda parameters and their respective errors, overall correlation value of all the nIDPs from test-dataset,

and the number of components with gut-brain mixture), into a two-dimensional space. From the UMAP clustering, we could select centroid models for in-depth inspection and behavioural prediction. These intermediate analyses thus integrate tens of thousands of candidate latent structures to identify multivariate gut–brain patterns with maximal behavioural relevance.

Figure 2: Five clusters derived from UMAP clustering obtained after filtering procedures. This clustering projects the clusters of 11 model parameters into a two-dimensional space. The UMAP dimensions depicted are therefore a dimensionality-reduced representation of the 11 model parameters.

1.1.1 Intermediate results

The intermediate analyses yielded robust multivariate components linking gut microbiota composition with large-scale resting-state connectivity. Across the filtered solution space, multiple components showed meaningful modality mixture, with microbiome contributions often exceeding 60–70% and brain contributions distributed across SN, DMN, and LN networks.

From the five centroid models emerging from the clustering solution, one cluster and its centroid model (Model 3280) consistently produced latent components—in the case of Model 3280; Component 93—characterized by a strong mixture across modalities (Model3280: 71.3% microbiome; 17.3% LN; 11.1% DMN).

This component showed:

- Positive loadings in taxa such as UCG-010, DTU089 belonging to *Oscillospirales*, CAG-56 belonging to *Lachnospiraceae*, and *Lactobacillus* ($z > 2$),
- Negative loadings in *Collinsella* and *Eubacterium siraeum* group ($z < -2$), highlighting a distributed microbial signature relevant for behavioural prediction.

Brain network contributions of this component involved:

- LN clusters in nucleus accumbens and amygdala,
- DMN clusters in medial prefrontal cortex and precuneus, consistent with reward valuation, stress responsivity, and affective regulation circuits.

We further display the full model 3280 for visualisation and explanation purposes. In Figure 3 we display the performance of this model in prediction of nIDPs, as well as the modality contribution weights and the prediction weights. In order to achieve a physiologically meaningful model, we argue a model needs to meaningfully reconstruct the IDPs, thus it needs to reconstruct brain networks and microbiome. In order to link gut and brain, a model also needs to contain components that link the IDP modalities statistically. Lastly, and importantly for the supervised approach, these components should be optimized for their predictive performance on the selected nIDPs. We safeguard overfitting by cross-validation and by using the extracted individual features of meaningful models for prediction of unseen behavioural variables.

Figure 3: Summary of the selected model (3820)

a) model fit (predicted vs. true values) for each nIDP from the test (blue) vs the training (green) dataset (total of 12 model fits). b) heat maps of the modality weights for each component of each modality input (on the left) and c) the prediction weights for each component of each nIDP.

Component 93 also exhibited strong associations with behavioural and psychological nIDPs, most prominently:

- BMI (weight = 1.81),
- Anxiety Sensitivity (ASI) (0.36),
- Life event impact (0.73).

When tested in out-of-sample prediction using the independent Food Auction Task (FAT), this component significantly predicted:

- valuation of unhealthy vs. healthy food items ($\beta = 0.17$, $p = 0.026$),
- choice of unhealthy vs. healthy items ($\beta = 0.16$, $p = 0.010$).

These findings provide compelling intermediate evidence for a multivariate gut–brain phenotype jointly reflecting microbial composition, limbic/DMN connectivity, affective traits, and eating-related behaviour. Importantly, these effects emerged in a healthy, deeply phenotyped human cohort, supporting the feasibility of robust gut–brain linkage discovery at population scale. We will continue to explore and describe the current model space. Model 3280 and its component 93 are to the best of our current knowledge representative of their model space and cluster. We’re currently still validating model space stability and sensitivity to parameter modulation.

Ongoing work focuses on validating the observed signatures longitudinally and across tasks relevant to stress and hedonic eating.

1.2 Outlook

Within HEREDITARY, in March 2024 we have submitted all fecal samples of HBS for DNA extraction and 16s rRNA sequencing of the V3-V4 region with Illumina Novaseq 6000. The relative abundances were ready for integration in December 2024. Thus, these intermediate analyses are based on the sample. Based on the microbiome composition results, we have evaluated potential targets for metabolic parameters and are currently screening options to run a short-chain fatty acid panel on the feces data.

In the upcoming year, the HEREDITARY project will conduct two more hypothesis-driven studies investigating the relationships between stress, diet, microbiome composition, brain connectivity, and eating behaviour. Study 1 aims to determine whether elevated hedonic food valuation and choices are driven by stress, anxiety, and dietary factors, mediated by multivariate associations between the gut microbiome and reward-related brain connectivity. Study 2 will explore whether these associations explain stress-related eating in daily life. The analysis will employ data from the Healthy Brain Study, focusing on multimodal datasets including resting-state fMRI, gut microbiota profiles, stress responses, and behavioural measures from a food auction task. LICA will integrate these data to uncover joint contributions of brain and gut features in predicting food choices and stress-induced eating patterns. Longitudinal and exploratory approaches will further validate findings and assess robustness.

Furthermore, we will apply the models from these intermediate analyses to explain clinical phenotypes in the MindSet dataset.

2 Conclusions

Within the HEREDITARY project, the present intermediate analyses demonstrate the feasibility and added value of supervised multimodal integration for uncovering robust gut–brain linkages in large, deeply phenotyped human cohorts. By extending earlier unsupervised Linked ICA approaches with SuperBigFLICA, we show that joint patterns of gut microbiota composition and large-scale resting-state connectivity can be identified that are not only physiologically interpretable, but also optimized for behavioural and clinical relevance. Importantly, these multivariate signatures emerge in a healthy population and generalize to independent behavioural outcomes, underscoring their robustness and translational potential.

The identified components integrate relative abundance of microbial genera with limbic and default-mode network connectivity, and relate meaningfully to anxiety, life stress, BMI, and eating-related behaviour. This aligns closely with HEREDITARY’s overarching aim to move beyond pairwise associations and towards multivariate, systems-level characterizations of gut–brain interactions. By systematically exploring and filtering a large model space, and by validating predictive performance out of sample, these analyses establish a principled framework for identifying candidate gut–brain phenotypes that are both statistically stable and biologically plausible.

This work provides a methodological and empirical foundation for the next phases of HEREDITARY. Applying these or similar models to the MindSet clinical cohort will directly address disease relevance by examining whether the same multivariate gut–brain signatures explain variation in psychopathology and maladaptive eating in psychiatric populations.

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The bibliographic entries are arranged in lexicographical order based on the key, following the APA style. This enables us to place the entries and citations in the table and text in any sequence, allowing for later sorting while ensuring consistency.

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